

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CHALLENGES OF PROGRAM BUDGETING PLANNING IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

One of the key directions of the Georgian budget system is program budgeting. The main advantage of the program budget is that it allows the budget to be oriented towards specific directions and final results, as well as clear cause-and-effect relationships - between specific financial resources and achieved results.

Although the preparation of the program budget began years ago, it is still not approved by the Budget Law and is only an appendix, which represents a significant challenge for the Georgian financial system and, accordingly, for the budget system. Despite the improvement of information on programs, sub-programs and their expected results and evaluation indicators, it still requires further refinement and additional improvements.

Keywords: 1. Budget system; 2. Budget; 3. Program budget; 4. Budget planning; 5. Budget indicators.

Introduction: Program budget planning is characterized by significant features and its goal is to achieve acceptable medium-term and final financial results. The main task of program budget planning is to align the resources needed and available to achieve the program's goal. Therefore, first the results and the indicators by which they are measured should be planned, and then the costs necessary to achieve the result should be determined. Over the years, the stages of transition to program budgeting have been a rather difficult and time-consuming process, since the program budget planning methodology, in turn, includes the following areas: discussion of the first stage of the budget planning process in the country's basic data and directions document and assessment of the information contained therein in relation to the budget process; program budget structure; determination of the main categories of program classification; discussion of the sub-programs constituting the program, indicators for assessing the planned final results and achieved results, information on sources and volume of financing. Although information on expected results and evaluation indicators of programs and sub-programs has improved, it still requires further refinement and additional improvements.

Review: One of the important issues in the development of the Georgian budget system is programmatic budgeting. The main advantage of programmatic budgeting is that it allows the budget to be determined on specific directions, planned results and achieved final results. The preparation of programmatic budgets has been underway in Georgia for several years since 2012, although it has not yet been approved by the Budget Law and is only an appendix.

In the process of programmatic budgeting, the main attention is focused on the expected results of planned programs and includes the following main indicators: main indicators of the state budget; state

budget revenues; state budget expenditures; non-financial assets and their functional classification; changes in the total balance of the state budget and financial assets and liabilities, and state budget priorities and programs, as a set of measures to be implemented to achieve the goals of the priorities defined by the budget, which are grouped according to similar content and are implemented in the long term to achieve the final result.

State budget programs can be of the following types in terms of content: management and regulation, service, subsidy and infrastructure, which combine relevant administrative and service measures aimed at the proper functioning of the financial system and related to the development of state and financial policy in the relevant areas.

According to the duration of the program, it can be: current, one-year and multi-year, after which it is necessary to divide it into main directions or sub-programs. Sub-programs, in turn, are divided into the same types in terms of content as programs, which are related to intermediate results, contribute to the achievement of the final result of the program and in terms of their content should be written in terms of the planned year and with a specific result, which can be achieved within one accounting year. The purpose of each sub-program written in the budget is to determine the volume of financing and planned activities. Programs that are mainly related to the implementation of infrastructure projects can be divided not into sub-programs, but into various capital projects, although the aforementioned projects are also sub-programs in their content.

The preparation of the budget in a programmatic format includes information on the expected results of the programs defined within the framework of priorities and their evaluation indicators. Programmatic budgeting of the state budget in Georgia includes the following main directions and by 2024 amounted to:

➤ Financing of health and social protection programs 7 829.2 million GEL;

- Financing of culture and sports programs from the consolidated budget 840.0 million GEL, and within the framework of the state budget 472.0 million GEL;
- Financing of environmental protection programs up to 180.0 million GEL;
- Financing of agricultural programs more than 580.0 million GEL;
- Financing of existing programs aimed at supporting small and medium-sized businesses more than 300.0 million GEL.

Although the data on the expected results and outcome assessment indicators of programs and subprograms have improved, shortcomings were identified in the following two main areas: shortcomings in the planning process and shortcomings in the performance reporting process.

Of the shortcomings in the planning process, the process of developing medium-term action plans and the information presented therein in particular require qualitative improvement, as the breakdown of programs and subprograms into detailed measures, the separation of competencies of implementers of measures, the definition of baseline and target indicators of measures, the indication of the data source for measuring indicators, the determination of the need for additional funding, and the discussion of the relevant scenario are not fully carried out. Part of the final and intermediate results do not have target indicators, which makes it impossible to assess the results and effectiveness achieved by the programs at the reporting stage. Therefore, it is not possible to report on the planned and actual results. Some of the evaluation indicators for some programs and sub-programs cannot provide a measure of the achieved results and assess the effectiveness of the program. In addition, some programs and sub-programs require additional indicators for evaluation in order to fully assess the achieved results.

Among the shortcomings in the performance reporting process, it is worth noting that the performance reporting does not fully include information on all programs and sub-programs for which expected results and indicators for evaluating results were determined at the planning stage.

In the case of certain programs, no explanation is provided for the differences between planned and achieved results, or the explanation provided is of a general nature and it is impossible to determine what caused the deviation. In the case of certain programs, there is no complete reporting on achieved results or evaluation of results in relation to predetermined indicators.

In the case of some programs and sub-programs, the presentation of achieved results is carried out in a manner inconsistent with the indicators determined at the planning stage, which makes it difficult or impossible to compare planned and achieved results.

Conclusion: Program budgeting, as an alternative to the traditional budget, is one of the most important tools of modern public finance management, the purpose of which is to allocate state resources according to the achievement of specific programs and results. Unlike traditional, cost-oriented budgeting, the program approach makes it possible to determine whether the planned goals of the program and its performance indicators, through which the achieved result should be measured, are achieved. Particular attention is paid to the results that society should receive from budget implementation. This system allows state governance to plan priorities more effectively, increase transparency and improve accountability to citizens.

Program budgeting in Georgia is gradually approaching international standards, but its full-fledged implementation still faces significant challenges. Therefore, studying this issue is important both for increasing the efficiency of state governance and for the optimal use of financial resources and strengthening citizens' trust.

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